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The American response to the growth of Nasserism in Libya, 1951-1959

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The rise of Libya to statehood in 1951¹ coincided with the emerging of potent nationalism in the Middle East in general and in Egypt in particular that was attractive to many Libyans who hoped that independence would be just the first step toward the realization of their ultimate objectives of full union with the Arab world and the elimination of foreign bases on Libyan soil. The next several years, therefore, provided ambivalent progress. Although the Arab League admitted Libya in 1953, the United States concluded an agreement to continue its lease of Wheelus Air Field with the new Libyan government in 1954. For its part, the U.S. government sought a continuing friendship with an independent Libya that would allow a continuing American military presence in North Africa and that would prevent Communist penetration of the Mediterranean and North Africa. Therefore, Egyptian influence in Libya was the most significant challenge to Libyan-American relations for both the Libyan and U.S. governments throughout the 1950s and 1960s. But Egyptian influence was difficult to contain given the close historical relations between Libya and its neighbor, the attractiveness of Nasserism, and social relations between the Libyan and Egyptian people on all levels. Other neighboring North African countries that were pro-western, especially Tunis and Morocco, did not exercise the same type of influence over Libya, despite the fondest wishes of the government in Tripoli.

From the perspective of the Libyan government, too many were substituting Arab nationalism for Libyan patriotism.² The politicians and statesmen backed the king, who advocated an independent foreign policy for Libya that promised to avoid the hazards of a Nasserist foreign policy that might endanger Libyan interests with other countries and complicated its foreign relations, especially with western countries such as the United States and Britain. To these Libyan

¹ Libya was Italian colony 1911- 1943. In the second war, Libyan leaders _especially Idris Sanusi who became King of Libya when get independence_ joined the war as allied against Italy. After the war, It administered by French-British administration until 1951 when get independent through the United Nations backed by Britain and the United States, which already had military presence since the war and kept that presence after independence in order to prevent U.S. interests from Russian penetration because they realized the importance of strategic location of Libya in Mediterranean region during the war. Therefore, Libya established close friendship relations with Britain and the United States, signing two major treaties with them that considered the core of its relations with the west in turn of their financial assistance to the new weak state. For more details see: Majid Khadduri, *Modern Libya: A Study in Political Development* (Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1963), Adrian Pelt, *Libyan Independence and the United Nations: A Case of Planned Decolonization* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 1970), and Scott L. Bills, *The Libyan Arena: The United States, Britain, and the Council of Foreign Ministers, 1945-1948* (Kent, OH: Kent State University Press, 1995)

² Mohamed Banon, interview by author, Cincinnati, OH, 2016, and Mahmoud El-Deek, interview by author, Huntsville, AL, 2015, both in author's possession.

statesmen, the reality was that their country was a new, poor, and weak country.³ Furthermore, Egypt—based on its own historical experience--adopted an anti-monarchical policy that directly threatened the monarchies in Libya, Iraq, and Saudi Arabia. Such policies also attracted the approval of the Soviet Union, so Tripoli considered Nasserism a double threat to Libyan-American relations.⁴

Unsurprisingly, the United States paid close attention to what was happening in Libya. For example, the June 1956 National Intelligence Estimate reported that

“Libya’s foreign policy is likely to be ambivalent. The king tends to be pro-US, but his principal advisers and possible successors, including Ben Halim, [he was Prime Minister of Libya 1953-57 who signed the agreement of 1954 of Wheelus Field which is considered the core of friendship between Libya and the united states] are more opportunistic. Despite Libya’s dependent on U.S. and U.K financial subsidies, it is sympathetic with the anti-colonial and anti-western feelings of the Arab world, and is subject to extensive Egyptian influence. Libyan leaders fear Egyptian domination and suspect Egyptian intentions,⁵

Based on subsequent developments, such fears seem to have been justified, for the next year’s National Security Report pointed to the many ways in which the Egyptians were infiltrating and influencing Libyans:

Egypt has, since 1951, continuously sought to bring Libya into the Egyptian orbit. By supplying advisers and officials to the Libyan federal and provincial governments and teachers for the Libyan schools, and through the use of the Egyptian radio, movies, and newspapers, Egypt has spread Egyptian propaganda and influence in the country. The Egyptian embassy has aggressively tried to extend Egyptian influence and during the Suez crisis of the late 1956, sought to foment disorders. The Libyan government and the king have become fearful of Egyptian motives and have initiated steps to counteract Egyptian influence.⁶

³ Khadduri, *Modern Libya*, 330-35.

⁴ David A. Nichols, *Eisenhower 1956: The President’s Year of Crisis: Suez and the Brink of War* (New York: Simon and Schuster, 2011), 89.

⁵ National Intelligence Estimate, June 19, 1956, *Foreign Relations of United States, 1955-57*, vol. XVIII: *Africa* (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, 1989), 455 [hereafter *FRUS*].

⁶ National Security Council Report 5716/1, June 29, 1957, *FRUS, 1955-57*, 18: 492.

In this context, the United States recognized the significance of Egyptian influence in Libya. In November 1955, Under Secretary of State Herbert Hoover Jr sent a letter to the U.S. Secretary of Defense warning that “Libya, as an Arab state and neighbor to Egypt, is obviously susceptible to the influence of Egypt and appears to be under strong temptation to adopt Egyptian tactics in the conflict between east and west.”⁷ When U.S. Vice President Richard Nixon visited Libya in 1957, Ben Halim pointed out the popularity of the Nasserist approach among the masses in Libya, saying “Nasser plays strongly on the Israel question to arouse the emotions of the Arab people.”⁸ Both Halim and Nixon worried that these appeals would drag the Libyan government toward an anti-western Nasserist policy, even if both believed such a policy would run against Libyan interests, which had been linked with American interests in the region. In the light of Nasserist interests that seemed to work against U.S. interests in the region, the United States worked in concert with Libyan efforts to counter Egyptian efforts. For example, Director of the International Cooperation Administration (ICA) pointed out in November 1956 that the Libyan government had closed secondary schools in the province of Tripolitania following “civil disturbances” there led by some of the “700 subsidized Egyptian teachers” in the nation’s school system and had asked the ICA to help “recruit Arabic-speaking, non-Egyptian teachers.” It was also withdrawing “approximately 300 Libyans who are studying at the University of Cairo.”⁹ Nonetheless, the problem persisted so that it was the subject of concern of Marcus Gordon, Director of the U.S. Operations Mission in Libya. Although he thought it would be best to eliminate all Egyptian teachers in Libya and therefore reduce the opportunities for Communist infiltration, he recognized that this would be difficult given the work of the Egyptian cultural attaché in Tripoli.¹⁰

In an effort to counteract the influence of these Egyptian teachers, the United States created (1) a scholarship program for Libyans to study abroad elsewhere than Egypt, (2) a teacher replacement program, and (3) a construction program for a Libyan teachers’ training college and

⁷ Letter from the Acting Secretary of State to the Secretary of Defense Charles E. Wilson, November, 12, 1955, *FRUS, 1955-57*, 18: 419.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ As quoted in St. John Ronal Bruce, *Libya and the United States: Two Centuries of Strife*, (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2002), 73.

¹⁰ Telephone conversation on Egyptian teachers in Libya, March 12, 1958, Dwight D. Eisenhower Presidential Library (hereafter DEPL), Dennis A. Fitzgerald Papers, 1945-69, box 26, file: telephone conversations March-April 1958 (4).

English-language training program.¹¹ For example, on February 12, 1958, sixteen Libyan students who had graduated from the University of Cairo arrived for one to three years of advanced study in the United States, and 22 secondary-school students were sent to the U.K. for four to seven years of advanced study.¹² But the United States also prevented these scholarships from going to students who endorsed Nasserism and would not allow the successful applicants to even travel through Egypt or on Egyptian air lines.¹³ In the same context, the United States pleaded with its diplomatic missions in India, Iraq, Lebanon, Pakistan, Tunisia, and Turkey to provide Libya with Arabic-speaking teachers, but although they enjoyed some success in Lebanon, these efforts reduced the overall number of Egyptian teachers only intermittently.¹⁴ Additionally, they successfully recruited ninety new Arabic-speaking teachers who were Palestinian refugees; although they were naturally Arab nationalists, both Washington and Tripoli believed they would be less likely than Egyptian to act as agents of the new United Arab Republic (UAR).¹⁵ In addition, the United States committed to provide \$380,000 for salaries, travel, and audiovisual material for the new teachers.¹⁶

The U.S. launched a parallel campaign in higher education aimed at limited the flow of Egyptian professors into the country. In 1955, it sponsored staff and faculty members at the new Libyan University (later renamed Gar Younis University). The experience of Dr. Majid Khadduri exemplified U.S. efforts in this context. He was sent to work at Libyan University as Dean of the College of Arts and Education in 1957 in the framework of cultural assistance from the U.S. government. Initially, Khadduri worked in cooperation with the Libyan Minister of Education to nominate and assign several U.S. professors to fulfill university needs, but the two education

¹¹ Operation Coordinating Board (hereafter OCB) report (5712/1) on Libya, April 2, 1958, DEPL, White House Office (hereafter WHO), Office of the Special Assistant for NSC Affairs, records 1952-61, NSC series, briefing notes subseries, box 12, folder: U.S. policy toward Libya, 2.

¹² OCB report on U.S. policy toward Libya, March 12, 1958, DEPL, WHO, Office of the Special Assistant for NSC Affairs, records 1952-62, NSC series, policy papers subseries, box 21, file 5716/1: U.S. policy toward Libya, pp. 2-3, 7.

¹³ Majidi Rashad Abdel-Ghani, *El-Alakat Elibia Elmisria 1945-1969* [Egyptian-Libyan relations, 1945-1969] (Cairo: Alhayya Al-Misria Lilkitab, 2007), 275.

¹⁴ National Security Council Report 6004/1, March 15, 1960, *FRUS, 1958-1960*, vol. XIII: *Arab-Israeli Dispute, United Arab Republic, North Africa* (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, 1992), 743; Bruce, *Libya and the United States*, 74; OCB weekly activity report, September 16, 1957, DEPL, WHO, NSC staff, records 1948-61, OCB Secretariat series, box 8, file #1(3), p. 3.

¹⁵ OCB report on U.S. policy toward Libya, November 5, 1958, DEPL, WHO, Office of the Special Assistant for NSC Affairs, records 1952-62, NSC series, policy papers subseries, box 21, p. 3.

¹⁶ OCB weekly activity report, September 16, 1957, DEPL, WHO, NSC staff, records 1948-61, OCB Secretariat series, box 8, file #1(3), p. 3.

administrators soon differed on the issue of Egyptian professors. While Khadduri advocated for two “first-rate professors from the United States” as well as applicants from Iraq and Jordan, the Minister of Education insisted on ten Egyptian professors whom he had invited to join the faculty when he had visited Egypt.”¹⁷ Khadduri justified his position based on a combination of “high academic standing” as well as the desirability of having a professoriate drawn from a variety of countries, “not from one only.”¹⁸ Khadduri made his case to Libya’s King Idris, threatening to resign his position as Dean if a better outcome could not be secured. Similarly, U.S. embassy complaints led to long and fractious meetings with the Libyan Ministry of Education in Bayyadah (east Benghazi 200 km). The meetings resulted no serious thing at time so that and Khadduri left the university to be back his position in Wisconsin University. Khadduri and U.S. embassy members were disappointed at him and they described him as arrogant and he had not earnest intention to argue the problem.¹⁹ One final, smaller way in which the U.S. sought to limit Egyptian influence in Libya was by strengthening the Benghazi radio station to counter the popularity of Egyptian radio, especially the Arab Voice.²⁰ So, the United States worked at all levels to limit Egyptian influence internally and locally, and in this next section, we will see how it also sought to do this in Libya’s external relations.

In particular, the United States encouraged Libya to strengthen its relations with the pro-western countries of Middle East (such as Turkey, Iraq, and Lebanon) and to minimize its involvement in divisive Middle East problems and disputes.²¹ These efforts resulted in a Libyan-Saudi Arabian rapprochement that culminated with a visit by King Saud to Libya on his way back from the United States in 1957, which was meant to highlight both countries cooperation with the Eisenhower Doctrine.²² Furthermore, the United States worked to form a broader North African political association, initially including Libya, Tunisia, and Morocco and then adding Algeria after that nation attained its independence. Such an association was meant to be a counter balance to Nasserism. Tunisia’s first president, Habib Ben Ali Bourguiba, was the ideal leader, since he and

¹⁷ National Archives, Memorandum to Ambassador Tappin from Khadduri: Libyan University, June 1957, central files, Department of State.

¹⁸ Ibid.

¹⁹ National Archives, Edwin L. Smith “Observations of Libyan University’s American Dean on the Eve of his Departure,” central files, Department of State, August 7, 1957.

²⁰ Majdi Rashad Abdel-Ghani, *El-Alakat Elibia Elmisria 1945-1969* [Egyptian-Libyan relations, 1945-1969] (Cairo: Alhayya Al-Misria Lilkitab, 2007), 275.

²¹ National Security Council Report 6004/1, March 15, 1960, *FRUS, 1958-1960*, 13: 748-49; National Security Council Report 5716/1, June 29, 1957, *FRUS, 1955-57*, Africa, 18: 493-94.

²² Abdel-Ghani, *El-Alakat Elibia Elmisria 1945-1969*, 272.

Nasser promoted different ideologies and feuded with one other sharply. For this reason, the United States encouraged “Libya’s disposition to draw more closely politically, culturally and economically to Tunisia and Morocco.”²³ American policymakers especially saw this as a needed counter to Libya’s membership in the Arab League influence; a strongly pro-western or even a neutral Libya would also help insulate the rest of North Africa from Egyptian intrigue—a goal shared by both sides Bourguiba and the United States.²⁴

Such a North African confederation served both U.S. security interests in this region²⁵ and Libyan leaders’ goals of strengthening their nation’s standing and insulating it from the anti-monarchical and pro-United Arab Republic sentiments emanating from Egypt. Therefore, in January 1957, Tunisia’s Bourguiba and Libya’s Ben Halim signed a treaty of fraternity and good-neighborliness between their two countries. After a preamble stressing the nations’ sense of solidarity and their obligations of mutual defense, the treaty laid out concrete measures to bring the two countries into greater harmony, including ending customs barriers and restrictions on tourists, simplifying laws and tax regulations, building new means of transportation and communication, and providing mutual assistance in such matters as teaching, sanitation, and technology. At the treaty-signing ceremony, Bourguiba asserted, “We have the conviction that in the Arab countries of North Africa, there exists a Mahgrebian solidarity imposed by economic, historical, and geographic imperatives . . . our efforts have led us to harden that solidarity not in order to direct it against any other power, but in order to make of it an instrument of cooperation with the rest, particularly with the Western world of which we form a part.”²⁶ Immediately following the signing, mixed commissions were created to effect these provisions, and soon Tunisian professors, technicians, and engineers began to replace their Egyptian counterparts in Libya.²⁷ In conclusion, in this case, the United States successfully secured its strategic needs in the North African/Mediterranean region by pitting Bourguiba’s aspirations to regional leadership against Nasser’s and by encouraging a nervous Libyan government to unite with Tunisia and Morocco.

²³ National Security Council Report 5716/1, June 29, 1957, *FRUS, 1955-57*, 18: 494-95.

²⁴ Lorna Hahn, *North Africa: Nationalism to Nationhood* (Washington, DC: Public Affairs Press, 1960), 240-41.

²⁵ National Security Council Report 5911/1, November 4, 1959, *FRUS, 1958-1960*, 8: 615; Lorna Hahn, “Last Chance in North Africa,” *Foreign Affairs* 36, no. 2 (June 1958): 302-3.

²⁶ As quoted in Hahn, “Last Chance in North Africa,” 309.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, 308-9; Hahn, *North Africa*, 240.